

Key Concepts: Structural Model of Personality

INTRODUCTION: Freud proposed id-ego-superego as a structural model of personality (Cherry, Fulford et al.). An alternative is mind-body. Opportunity exists to translate id-ego-superego from psychiatric jargon to political jargon and to sort it in treat-first-what-kills-first order per opinion.

METHOD: The sampling of products is snowball sampling. The first participant is the author. The analyser is the author.

RESULT: The result is that of a trias politica id is legislative power, ego is executive power, and superego is judiciary power. Stress is corruption. The treat-first-what-kills-first order is executive-legislative-judiciary.

DISCUSSION: The result changes the trend of naming one of the three structures ego, i.e. I, to naming the whole ego. Future work could be to discuss renaming personality in personality disorder to judiciary and self in self-care to executive. Furthermore, it could be to discuss more opportunities between psychiatry and politics to research stress related terms, e.g. burnout. Furthermore, it could be to discuss the difference between stress and distress which looks analogical to stress and strain in physics. Furthermore, the iconological interpretation of stress as whether or not stress should be expected in difficult situations could be discussed. WHO answers that stress should be expected in difficult situations (WHO).

References

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